

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

RESEARCH OF DYNAMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF CNC LATHES

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Abstract

The article presents the methodology and results of experimental studies of the dynamic characteristics of a CNC lathe. The sequence of conducting research, the necessary apparatus and equipment are recommended. The influence of the dynamic characteristics of the main components of the machine on the accuracy of the shape of the cross-section of the surfaces of the parts processed on it was evaluated, and ways of improving the quality of turning processing were recommended.

Keywords: CNC lathe, dynamic characteristics, accuracy of parts processing.

The occurrence of oscillating processes in machine tools negatively affects the accuracy and quality of the machined surfaces of parts, reduces the technological capabilities of the machine tool. The availability of knowledge about the real dynamic characteristics of individual components of the machine tool makes it possible to determine ways to improve the dynamic quality and to develop recommendations for improving its design. Experimental determination of frequencies of self-oscillations of components and elements of the machine tool, their spectral analysis allows to determine resonant phenomena during the operation of the machine and to recommend measures to reduce their harmful effects [1].

Experimental researches of the dynamic characteristics of lathes are recommended to be carried out in the following sequence: - determination of natural oscillation frequencies of individual units of the machine; - determination of frequency spectra of relative oscillations of the tool and workpiece without cutting at different spindle rotation frequencies and during cutting; - definition of logarithmic decrements of oscillations of machine tool units.

To register and analyze vibrations, it is necessary to have equipment for vibration diagnostics with piezoelectric accelerometers, an analog-to-digital converter and a computer program for frequency analysis of vibrations. When registering the relative vibrations of the tool and the workpiece at idle speed and during cutting, it is effective to use a vibration meter with a non-contact eddy current sensor.

When determining the natural frequencies of oscillations of the units, measurements are performed in

the planes perpendicular and parallel to the bed guides, parallel to the directions of the P_y and P_z components of the cutting force. The impact on the object of measurement is carried out by an impulse impact, and free damping oscillations are simultaneously recorded along two coordinates. Accelerometers are installed using permanent magnets on the surfaces of the corresponding unit of the machine tool.

To determine the values of natural frequencies oscillations of units; frequencies with the highest levels of vibration acceleration are selected from the spectrum (amplitude-frequency characteristic). Further, these data are compared with the graphs of changes in the amplitude of oscillations over time after the impulse exposure, and a conclusion is made about the actual values of the frequencies of natural oscillations of units under research.

Vibrometer with a non-contact eddy current sensor is used to study the relative vibrations of the tool and the workpiece without cutting and during cutting. Sensor is fixed on the faceplate of the turret head of the machine in such a way that there is a gap of 0.5-0.8 mm between its measuring surface and the cylindrical mandrel clamped in the chuck of the lathe. Vibrometer registers the fluctuations of the gap between the mandrel and the measuring surface of the sensor. The dimensions of the mandrel and the measurement scheme are shown in Fig. 1. To reduce the impact of the mandrel runout, it is necessary to ensure its accurate installation in the spindle chuck with a radial runout of no more than $1\mu\text{m}$, or after installation in the chuck, perform a clean turning of the measuring surface of the mandrel, which will compensate for the errors of installation [2].

Fig. 1. The dimensions of the mandrel with a set of replaceable sample parts (a) and the arrangement of sensors during the determination of the relative vibrations of the cutting tool and the workpiece during cutting (b), where 1 – the mandrel with the replaceable sample part, 2 – the faceplate of the turret head, 3 – toolholder, 4 – eddy current sensor, 5 and 6 – accelerometers

In the course of research, the natural oscillation frequencies of the following units of the lathe model 1П420ПФ40 were determined: - a short mandrel with a length of 150 mm and a diameter of 40 mm, when measured at a distance of 100 mm from the end of the chuck; - turret head faceplate; - turret housing; - spindle headstock housing; - caliper slides, etc. (examples in the Table 1).

Table 1

Frequencies of free oscillations of units of the lathe in the range of 0-1000Hz

№	Measurement object	Basic frequency, Hz		Logarithmic decrement of oscillations, λ	
		Direction P_y	Direction P_z	Direction P_y	Direction P_z
1.	Mandrel in the chuck: projection 100mm, $d=40$ mm, length $l=150$ mm	432	450	0,25	0,34
2.	Turret head faceplate	120	110	0,52	0,57
3.	Turret head housing	265	265	0,3	0,27
4.	Longitudinal slides of the caliper	75	75	0,24	0,27
5.	Spindle headstock housing	97	97	0,77	0,77

The research of the relative vibrations of the cutter and the workpiece without cutting on the working lathe was carried out in the range of rotation frequencies of the spindle unit 200÷4000 rpm (3.33÷66.6 Hz) with a resolution of 200 rpm. In Fig. 2 shows the total spectrum of the maximum values of vibration accelerations in the frequency range 0÷100 Hz. Change in rotation frequency after 200 rpm allows you to introduce sequentially forced oscillations with a discreteness of 3.33 Hz into the system. The highest level of relative oscillations was registered at a frequency of 48.5 Hz

(51 dB). In the main drive of the lathe, which consists of a motor, a belt drive and a spindle assembly, the main source of the increased level of oscillations at a frequency of 48.5 Hz is the belt drive. By visual observations of the operation of the transmission during the experiment, an increase in the amplitudes of the belt oscillation was registered during the rotation of the spindle with frequencies close to 3000 rpm. The source of resonance was eliminated by introducing an additional belt tension roller into the belt drive.

Fig. 2. The total spectrum of the maximum values of vibration accelerations of the relative vibrations of the cutter and the workpiece without cutting during spindle rotation in the frequency range of 200÷4000 rpm with a discreteness of 200 rpm

The evaluation of the influence of the dynamic characteristics of the main components of the machine on the accuracy of the shape of the cross-section of the surfaces of the parts processed on it was carried out by processing a batch of steel parts by carbide plate cutter at cutting conditions that varied in the following range: cutting speed $V = 80\div 400$ m/min; feed $S = 0.06\div 0.3$ mm/rev; cutting depth $t = 0.5\div 2.5$ mm. Cutting researches were carried out according to the plan of a three-factor five-level experiment $3^5/36$ [3]. Errors of the shape of the cross section of the parts, which were estimated by deviations from roundness, at $S = 0.06$ mm/rev, $t = 0.5\div 1.5$ mm, $V = 100\div 300$ m/min did not exceed $3\ \mu\text{m}$.

In Fig. 3 shows an example of the circular graph of the surface of the processed sample No. 20 according to the plan of the experiment with cutting conditions $V = 373$ m/min (3500 rpm), $S = 0.12$ mm/rev, $t = 2.0$ mm. The circular graph shows the traces of relative oscillations of the cutter and the workpiece during cutting in the form of errors in the shape of the cross-section of the sample part. Oscillations with frequencies corresponding to multiple harmonics of the spindle rotation frequency are displayed on the circular graph in the form of facets. The reason of part facets may be the uneven stiffness along the angular coordinate of the clamping three-cam spindle chuck, which held the mandrel with the sample parts during cutting and was a source of parametric fluctuations.

Fig. 3. Circular graph of the surface of the processed part with cutting conditions $V = 325$ m/min (2800 rpm), $S = 0.24$ mm/rev, $t = 0.5$ mm

As a result of the data analysis according to the experimental plan $3^5/36$, a mathematical model with a multiple correlation coefficient of 0.973 and an approximation error of 9.12% was obtained. In Fig. 4 shows the results of calculating the dependence of the deviation from the roundness of the surfaces of the machined parts on the cutting mode. Optimization of the out-of-

roundness parameter by the minimum value for feed $S = 0.15$ mm/rev gave the following results: out-of-roundness - $1.22\ \mu\text{m}$; at $t = 1.0$ mm and $V = 170$ m/min. The analysis of the regression coefficients of the mathematical model showed that the deviation from the roundness of the machined surfaces of the parts is influenced by all the parameters of the cutting modes.

Fig. 4. Calculation results according to the plan of the experiment $5^3/36$ dependence of the non-roundness of the surfaces of the parts processed on the lathe 1П420ПФ40 from cutting speed V (m/min), feed S (mm/rev) at cutting depth $t = 0.5$ mm (a) and $t = 1.5$ mm (b)

Analysis of the data shown in Fig. 4, allows you to draw the following conclusions: - lathe model 1П420ПФ40 provide high accuracy and quality of parts processing, which in some cases allows to abandon the finishing operations of grinding; - rational conditions of turning steel parts with a carbide plate cutters have been determined to obtain the smallest processing errors; - the process of shaping the surface during cutting, which is determined by the relative oscillations of the cutter and the part, is influenced by the dynamic system of the machine tool, which includes the elastic subsystems of the spindle-chuck-part and caliper group, processes in drives and the cutting process.

Conducted vibration diagnostics of the lathe model 1П420ПФ40 made it possible to determine the natural frequencies and logarithmic decrements of oscillations of the main components of the machine tool, the dynamic characteristics of which mainly depend on its dynamic quality. In addition, the main factors whose dynamic characteristics have a significant impact on the accuracy of the machine tool are determined. These

include the basic components of the dynamic system of the lathe, the drive of the main movement with a belt transmission and the cutting process. The results of research of the dynamic characteristics of the machine tool were used in the development of a mathematical model of the closed dynamic system of the lathe.

References

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